

Final Requirements for Multimodal Exposome

Project title: Early Environmental quality and life-course mental health effects

Project Number: 874724

Project Acronym: Equal-Life

Work package WP5- Deliverable 5.5 – Final Requirements for Multimodal Exposome

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.1	2022-09-09	
1.2	2022-10-03	
1.3		

REVISION DATES		
Version	Publication date	Change
2.0		

H2020 program	Grant agreement numbers 874724 (Equal-Life),
Project start date: Jan 1st 2020	Duration: 60 months
Project Coordinator: Irene van Kamp (RIVM)	

WP (number and title)	Equal-Life WP5
Deliverable Number	Equal-Life D5.5
Deliverable Title	Final Requirements for Multimodal Exposome
Due date	30-06-2022
Actual date	03-10-2022
Dissemination Level	Public

D 5.5 - Final Requirements for Multimodal Exposome

Lead beneficiary	KI/TUD	
Responsible authors	Jenny Selander, Arzu Arat, Johanna Jonsson, Achilleas Psyllidis, Irene van Kamp	
E-mail / phone responsible authors	jenny.selander@ki.se / +46762095601	arzu.arat@ki.se / +46760494366
	johanna.jonsson@ki.se / +46737665367	A.Psyllidis@tudelft.nl /+31 (0)63 4648139
	Irene.van.kamp@rivm.nl +31 886893222	
Co-authors	Kerstin Persson Waye	
	Natalia Vincens	
	Katja Kanninen	
	Arto Alatalo	
	Aino-Kaisa Piironen	
	John Gulliver	
	Maria Klätte	
	Maria Foraster	
	Maud Dohmen	
	Hendriek Boshuijzen	
	Peter van den Hazel	
	Miriam Weber	
	Gordana Ristovska	
	Dick Botteldooren	
	Dirk Schreckenber	
	Jaakko Kaprio	
	Alyce Whipp	
	Kim White	
	Jordi Julvez	
	Janina Fels	
	Gabriele Bolte	
	Maddie White	

D 5.5 - Final Requirements for Multimodal Exposome

	Helene Gudi-Mindermann	
	Marco Brambilla	
	Ella Braat	
	Maarten Hornikx	
	Peter Lercher	
	Charlotte Clark	
	Christin Belke	
	Angel Dzhambov	
	Sarah Benz	
	Marja Heinonen-Guzejev	
	Antònia Valentin	
	Bruno Raimbault	
	Albert Ambrós	

Contents

1. Summary	7
2. Introduction and aim	8
3. Selecting relevant exposures for the main outcomes.....	9
3.1 Literature reviews	10
3.2 Defining the outcomes relevant for Equal-Life	10
3.2.1 Mental health.....	11
3.2.2 Cognitive development	13
3.3 Defining the mechanisms relevant for Equal-Life.....	14
3.3.1 Mechanism: Stress and restoration.....	15
3.3.2 Mechanism: Sleep	16
3.3.3 Mechanism: Self-regulation and coping	18
3.4 Stakeholder consultations and internal expert discussions.....	19
3.5 Defining the exposures relevant for Equal-Life	22
3.5.1 The internal exposome.....	22
3.5.2 The external exposome: physical exposome.....	24
3.5.3 The external exposome: social exposome.....	27
4. Final selection of the external exposome	28
4.1 Shortlist of key exposure variables.....	28
4.2 Data mapping and data harmonisation	30
4.3 Enrichment of exposures.....	31
4.3.1 Enrichment of built environment: co-accessibility	32
4.3.2 Enrichment of natural environment: vegetation indices.....	33
4.3.3 Enrichment of the social exposome	35
4.4 Operationalising the multimodal exposome	35
5. Conclusions and a way ahead.....	36
5.1 Summary	36
5.2 Strengths and weaknesses	36
5.3 Where we stand now and the way ahead	36
6. References.....	38
7. Annex	45
7.1 Annex 1: Mental health outcomes	45
7.2 Annex 2: Cognitive outcomes.....	47

7.3	Annex 3: Stress-related mechanisms	48
7.4	Annex 4: Restoration-related mechanisms.....	50
7.5	Annex 5: Sleep-related mechanisms	51
7.6	Annex 6: Self-regulation and coping-related mechanisms	52
7.7	Annex 7. Definitions of shortlisted exposures	53
7.8	Annex 8: External exposures rejected from the shortlist	57
7.9	Annex 9: Overarching research questions identified in Equal-Life	58

1. Summary

The main goal of the Equal-Life project is to study the impact of multimodal exposures on children's mental health and cognitive development (van Kamp et al., 2022). Multimodal hereby refers to multiple data modes being spatial, temporal, textual, or multimedia (such as street-level imagery) linked to exposures. The aim of this document is to provide an overview of the requirements for the multimodal data collection pertaining to enrichment of data, with emphasis on physical exposure including the natural and built environment. This work has been conducted in several tasks across multiple work packages within Equal-Life, and has involved literature reviews and stakeholder consultations, but most of all expert-based discussions and working sessions. Reasoning from the outcomes towards relevant exposures, parallel work mapped, grouped, and harmonised the existing exposome variables in the cohorts, and constructed overall research questions which guided the selection of the exposome variables further. This enabled the relevant exposome variables to be developed within the projects limited resources. The addition of the enriched variables will provide the Equal-Life project with a unique set of exposome variables to be used for assessment of the effects of physical and social environmental exposures on mental health and cognitive development of children from preconception to adolescence, and in extension provide a basis for new policies to prevent and/or reduce these outcomes.

This deliverable contains five chapters, structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 is composed of a brief introduction to the project overall, as well as the aim of this specific deliverable.
- Chapter 3 addresses the literature reviews, internal expert discussions, external stakeholder consultations and related tasks, and provides definitions of the outcomes, mechanisms and exposome targeted in Equal-Life.
- Chapter 4 describes the translation of information to a set of requirements and criteria for data enrichment in general, with a particular focus on the natural and built environment. Here, tasks geared towards finalizing the external exposome will be described, including identification of key exposure variables; mapping, grouping and harmonisation of available data; formulation of research questions; data enrichment; and a few words on further work with operationalising the multimodal exposome.
- Chapter 5 concludes this deliverable with a brief summary, the strengths and weaknesses of the work conducted within the context of this deliverable, as a few words on where we stand now and the way ahead.

Overall, focus will be on the arguments behind the decisions made and their results, rather than the underlying processes unless they are relevant for further activities and the Equal-Life tools to be developed. Supporting material is presented in the Annex.

2. Introduction and aim

The main goal of the Equal-Life project is to study the impact of multimodal exposures on children’s mental health and cognitive development (van Kamp et al., 2022). The Equal-Life project brings together eleven cohorts and school studies from seven different countries and contain information on children from conception to 21 years of age. The existing exposure data in these cohort and school studies will be enriched with novel data sources. In this document, the emphasis will be on the enrichment of natural and built environment data. By enriching the existing data, we will be able to capture additional parts of the physical exposome. Within the project, two main types of exposome are distinguished: the external exposome, further subdivided into the physical (e.g. aspects of the natural and built environment, indoor and outdoor environmental quality etc.) and social (e.g. societal context, socioeconomic, social, and psychosocial factors at the individual and community levels) exposome; and the internal exposome. The exposome and outcomes of relevancy in Equal-Life is visualised in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. An overview of the exposome, with its multiple parts, and outcomes of relevancy in Equal-Life.

The aim of this deliverable is to provide an overview of the requirements for the multimodal data collection pertaining to enrichment of exposure data, with emphasis on the natural and built environment. The requirements were identified by a series of tasks. One group of tasks included carrying out literature reviews, preparing definition documents and performing expert discussions and expert and stakeholder-consultations, leading to the further selection of outcomes and key exposome indicators. In parallel, the content and properties of the data available was determined by mapping, grouping and harmonising the available data in the

cohorts and school studies; and formulating research questions. These tasks together further informed the requirements for enrichment. All the above tasks were carried out with the child development perspective in mind. **Figure 2** schematically sketches the process by which the requirements were formulated.

Figure 2. An overview of the iterative process of preparing the requirements for the multimodal data exposome.

3. Selecting relevant exposures for the main outcomes

The concept of the exposome was first described by Christopher Paul Wild in 2005 to emphasise the importance of human environmental exposures (Wild, 2005). The need for the concept of exposome rose from scientific, political, and social goals to define methodological progress in exposure studies. The concept refers to the totality of exposures from a variety of external and internal exposures over a complete lifetime. Additionally, the concept reinforces the idea that everyone's health or disease is the product of the individual history of exposures.

Across the lifespan, an individual is exposed to a vast number of physical and social factors and internal responses to these. There are multiple ways to study mental health and cognitive development in children as dependent on these exposures, however, the totality of all the exposures and outcomes cannot be studied in one single project. Further, the relevance of the exposures is strongly dependent on the outcomes under study. Hence, one of the key tasks in Equal-Life was making decisions on *which* outcomes to focus on and *which* exposures (both traditional and innovative) are relevant for these outcomes, for specific age groups during childhood and adolescence. This was achieved by reasoning from the outcomes backwards to relevant exposures via key a-priori selected mechanisms, in an iterative fashion, between several main tasks carried out in parallel. These involved:

- **Literature reviews** resulting in theoretical frameworks and evidence papers on the key mechanism studied in Equal-Life (see the upcoming special issue “Exposome perspective on child health” in Environmental Research (ISSN 0013-9351)), as well as refinement of research questions and hypotheses.
- **Internal expert discussions** within a series of workshops resulting in decisions about the key domains, selection criteria and groups of exposure related variables, and also in a set of definition papers.
- **Expert and stakeholder consultations** using Delphi consultations, including internal and external surveys that contributed to a set of key research questions.
- **Mapping, grouping and harmonisation of the available data** which showed data availability in the included cohorts and school studies. This served the purpose of identifying where enrichment is needed and guiding the analyses.

3.1 Literature reviews

Literature reviews were carried out in order to develop a set of conceptual models and theoretical frameworks, and to describe the evidence in previous scientific literature on how three a priori identified mechanisms (stress and restoration; sleep; self-regulation and coping), affect by mediation or moderation the linkages between exposome and outcome. The aim was to develop a theoretical framework for the total exposome, including the social, physical and internal exposures, and their impact on mental health and cognitive development among children. In parallel, definition documents were prepared in order to frame definitions of the key outcomes, mechanisms and exposures, resulting in definition papers on, i) mental health and cognitive outcomes, ii) the key mechanisms (stress and restoration; sleep; self-regulation and coping), iii) the social and physical exposome, and finally, iv) the internal exposome. These are summarized below. For more details on the definition papers, the theoretical frameworks and evidence papers, we refer to the upcoming special issue of Environmental Research.

3.2 Defining the outcomes relevant for Equal-Life

At a conceptual stage of the project two main domains of outcomes were identified: mental health and cognitive development. For each of these outcomes, definition papers were prepared, which served as a basis for further work. Below a summary is provided of the key definitions of outcomes relevant for the project, including an overview of relevant mechanisms.

3.2.1 Mental health

There are several interrelated psychological concepts that are of interest and relevance to the characterization of mental health in the Equal-Life project. These include **mental health** (mental ill-health or illness) per se and **well-being** (positive mental health). Whilst the terms mental health (or mental ill-health or illness) and well-being are often used interchangeably, mental health typically refers to the presence of psychological or psychiatric illness or psychological ill-health (psychopathology), whereas well-being refers to positive psychological health. Mental health is usually assessed using measures defined by diagnostic systems as DSM-V or ICD-10¹ producing diagnoses of **depression** or **anxiety** in adolescence, or **ADHD** in childhood, or by symptom measures assessing internalizing and externalizing symptoms such as the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) in childhood (Goodman & Goodman, 2009). In childhood, it is less common to diagnose psychiatric disorders and more common to assess symptom measures of mental health covering **internalizing, externalizing, and thought disorders**. Disorders share symptoms and are comorbid across the life course, and many genes are implicated in many disorders. On this basis the general factor of psychopathology (the p-factor) has been put forward as a factor that disposes people to psychopathology (Caspi et al., 2014). A higher p-score is associated with greater life impairment, poorer developmental history and more compromised early-life brain function (Caspi et al., 2014). There is evidence that the p-factor explains mental illness in childhood and adolescence, as well as into mid-life and that it is stable over time (Caspi et al., 2020; Lahey et al., 2018; Pettersson, Lahey, Larsson, & Lichtenstein, 2018; Riglin et al., 2019).

Well-being, or positive mental health, defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as “*a state of well-being in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to her or his community*” (World Health Organization, 2004) has become a popular concept both within psychiatry (Keyes, 2007; Ryan & Deci, 2001; Slade, 2010; Weich et al., 2011) and with policy makers (Office for National Statistics UK, 2011). According to this definition, a healthy state is not merely the absence of diseases but also a sense of fulfilment, life satisfaction and motivation. Well-being is typically defined by two components: **hedonic well-being**, covering happiness, life satisfaction, and overall interest in life; and **eudaemonic well-being**, covering personal growth, relationships, and optimal functioning (Ryan & Deci, 2001; Stewart-Brown et al., 2009; Weich et al., 2011). Other definitions of well-being/positive mental health distinguish between “feeling well” (pleasure, happiness, emotional satisfaction) and “doing well” (adaptational success, i.e. mastering of developmental tasks faced by

¹ American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th Edition (DSM-5)*; WHO. (1992). *The ICD-10 Classification of Mental and Behavioural Disorders*. These are the most versions of these diagnostic disease classifications, which are typically updated every 10-15 years, hence the use of different versions across studies depending on when the research study was conducted. ICD-11 was released in 2018 and may be available in some more recent cohorts.

children of a given age in a specific socio-cultural context) (Masten & Curtis, 2000; Miles, Espiritu, Horen, Sebian, & Waetzig, 2010). The latter dimension has been shown to be associated with communication skills and educational achievement in children (O'Connor, O'Connor, Gray, & Goldfeld, 2018). Other terminology used in relation to well-being includes psychological well-being, social well-being and emotional-well-being. **Quality of life** refers to “an individual’s perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns. It is a broad ranging concept affected in a complex way by the person’s physical health, psychological state, personal beliefs, social relationships and their relationship to salient features of their environment.” (WHO, 1995). Quality of life is therefore associated with both well-being and potentially also mental health (Ravens-Sieberer, Karow, Barthel, & Klasen, 2014). The measurement of quality of life can cover diverse aspects including life satisfaction, functioning and health-related quality of life. Quality of life is often measured in terms of satisfaction with a series of domains, or overall life satisfaction, rather than the person’s emotional state measured in well-being. Health-related quality of life may often align more closely to the construct of well-being than quality of life, per se. The key mental health outcomes in Equal-Life are outlined in **Figure 3**, as well as in the tables in Annex 1.

Figure 3. An overview of the key mental health outcomes in Equal-Life.

Figure 3 represents the concepts as they were defined in the definition documents. Since then, there has been discussions and developments in the way mental health outcomes are grouped. In the case of diagnosis, we have added **autism** as an outcome of interest considering its prevalence within neurodevelopmental disorders. The “thought disorders” sub-division has been removed as a target-outcome in Equal-Life, as the focus is rather on symptoms and behaviour than on psychopathology at a later age (outside the scope of Equal-Life). Within the well-being outcome, we have decided to prioritise quality of life, happiness,

life satisfaction and social relationships as these outcomes have more complete data. The refinement of the outcomes is still work in progress.

3.2.2 Cognitive development

Cognition is defined as “*the mental action or process of acquiring knowledge and understanding through thought, experience, and the senses*” (Dhakal & Bobrin, 2022) In daily life, we need cognition to make sense out of the sensory input we receive, to learn from experience, and to interact appropriately and safely with the environment. From an information processing point of view (Neisser, 1967), cognition refers to perception and appropriate (re-)action, to encoding, storage, transformation, elaboration, and retrieval of information, to reasoning, problem-solving, and decision making. We will consider how the exposome affects children’s **cognitive functions** and **school achievement/academic attainment**, e.g. grades and school-leaving qualifications. Concerning cognitive functions, we will include **domain-general cognitive abilities**, i.e. abilities that affect performance in complex tasks across several domains; and **language functions**, including oral and written language skills and their specific precursors, as these skills are key competencies for school success and academic achievement (Council of Europe, 2018).

Concerning domain-general functions, the most basic ability is **processing speed**, i.e. the ability to provide speeded responses to simple, unambiguous stimuli. Processing speed increases with age until adolescence and is regarded as an indicator of the efficiency of information processing (Kail, 1991). Age-related improvements in processing speed contribute to age-related improvements in more complex abilities, including executive functions (Willoughby, Hong, Hudson, & Wylie, 2020) and reasoning (Kail, Lervag, & Hulme, 2016). Processing speed deficits are associated with language, learning, and attention disorders in children (for review, see Moll et al., 2016), and with mental health disorders in adolescence (Bachman et al., 2012). Beyond processing speed, Equal-Life will focus on attention control, working memory, and higher-order skills like reasoning, problem solving, and planning. Attention control and working memory constitute separate, but interrelated components of **Executive Function (EF)**. EF is an umbrella term referring to cognitive processes that enable volitional control of goal-directed behaviour. EFs allow us to inhibit impulsive but insufficient responses, to stay focused on a task in the presence of distracting stimuli, to avoid actions that bring immediate rewards but hinder achievement of long-term goals, and to adapt quickly and efficiently to changing requirements. The key cognitive developmental outcomes are outlined in **Figure 4**, as well as presented in more detail in the tables in Annex 2.

Figure 4. An overview of the key cognitive developmental outcomes in Equal-Life.

3.3 Defining the mechanisms relevant for Equal-Life

At an early stage of the project three mechanisms were identified and selected to be the focus of Equal-Life: i) stress and restoration, ii) sleep, and iii) coping and self-regulation. The definitions and key aspects of these mechanisms, as initially described in the definition documents, are outlined in the below sections and an overview is visually provided in Figure 5. For additional details related to the definitions, see Annex 3-6.

Figure 5. An overview of the key mechanisms in Equal-Life

3.3.1 Mechanism: Stress and restoration

Stress and restoration are assumed to play a fundamental role in the proposed mechanisms underlying the association between exposures and cognitive development and mental health in children. In general, stress can be defined as *“internal or external aversive stimuli that challenge the organism and threaten the homeostasis”*, so *“stress occurs when homeostasis is threatened or perceived to be so”* (Chrousos, 2009). Stressors are the stimuli/situations that can be categorised in physical stressors (e.g. noise or heat), social stressors (e.g. inter-relational conflicts), ecological stressors (e.g. unpleasant housing situation, lack of perceived safety), economic stressors (e.g. financial problems) or occupational stressors (e.g. time pressure, rush) (Bodenmann & Gmelch, 2009). In Equal-Life, most so-called stressors can be conceptualised as aspects of the physical, social and internal exposome.

In general, there are three main approaches to theorise stress: psychological, physiological, and neuro-psycho-biological. **Psychological theories** emphasise the intervening mechanisms between a stressor and its (long-term) effects. Cohen et al. (2007) describe that *“psychological stress occurs when an individual perceives that environmental demands tax or exceed his or her adaptive capacity”* (p. 1685). On the other hand, **physiological theories** emphasise the immediate physiological reaction between stressor and effect. Selye (1974) views stress as *“the nonspecific response of the body to any demand”* (p. 27). The stimulus stands for the stressor and the response equals stress. Note, that according to this definition stress can be a response to either a positive (challenge, eustress) or negative demand (aversive stressor, distress), indicating the physiological mobilization of the organism to deal with the demand. The physiological perspective of stress, as described here, refers to responses to acute demanding situations. In addition, acute stress indicators, i.e. biomarkers, are relevant and considered as predictors for long term effects (e.g. Babisch, 2002). This should be distinguished from chronic stress, which is the result of a long-term process of responding frequently to demanding situations that are perceived as harmful or dangerous (primary appraisal); combined with the insight to have less or no control or limited ability or opportunity to cope with these situations (secondary appraisal); also combined with lack of opportunities to recover from such demands (lack of restoration). Chronic stress is closely related to mental (un)well-being and, in the long run, associated with mental illness such as depression (Chrousos, 2009). In consequence, this may mean higher vulnerability or sensitivity to (future) acute demands. **Neuro-psycho-biological approaches** integrate the first two approaches. Koolhaas et al. (2011) *“propose that the term ‘stress’ should be restricted to conditions where an environmental demand exceeds the natural regulatory capacity of an organism, in particular situations that include unpredictability and uncontrollability”* (p. 1291). In the Cognitive Activation Theory of Stress (Ursin & Eriksen, 2004) a stress response results from a perceived *“discrepancy between what is expected to be ‘normal’ and what is happening in reality (actual value)”* (p. 572). *“This perceived discrepancy (i.e. the stressor) is assumed to induce neurophysiological activation. [...] Neurophysiological activation due to this*

discrepancy remains elevated until the organism has succeeded in reducing the disparity between expected (feared or desired) and actual values (of personal noise exposure, for example). If the difference between expected and actual values persists, arousal sustains and induces pathophysiological processes” (Riedel et al., 2017, p. 6).

Restoration can be defined as a process through which adaptive capacities diminished in ongoing efforts to meet adaptive demands are renewed, recovered, or re-established (Hartig, 2004). We can distinguish actual restoration and subjective restoration experience (Hartig, 2007). **Actual restoration** refers to the recovery of cognitive or other resources following exposure to a taxing environmental stimulus, while **perceived restoration** refers to the perceptions of the effect of restorative experience or how one restored one feels in some spatial or activity context (Hartig, 2016; Malekinezhad and Bin Lamit 2018).

Restorativeness/restorative quality can be defined as the potential restorative capacity of environment, surroundings, setting or activity. This can be divided into **perceived restorative quality, objective restorative quality**, i.e. the availability or accessibility to environments where “stressors” are absent or environmental attributes elicit fascination or promote acquisition of new adaptive resources, and **instoration** — a construct closely related to restoration; that is, an environment of high restorative quality can afford opportunities to acquire new adaptive resources, and in turn both can work together to support mental health/ cognition and foster health in general.

The stress-restoration cycles take place across different behaviour settings where stress and restoration occur and movements among them (Hartig et al., 2003). Importantly, restoration is carried by person-environment transactions and is not an automatic outcome of objective exposure or simply being in a particular environment during time one might have available for restoration (von Lindern et al., 2017). Environment’s restorative quality depends on its potential to both permit and promote restoration (Hartig, 2004). First, an absence of immediate threats to safety and a relative absence of perceived social and physical demands (e.g. crowding, noise or other obligations) in an environment allows psychological distance from mental routines and demands. Second, attention can go effortlessly to interesting, pleasant aspects of the environment, thereby promoting faster and more complete decline in psychophysiological activation and giving rest to the neurocognitive mechanism on which directed attention is thought to depend (Kaplan & Kaplan, 1989; Kaplan, 1995; Ulrich, 1983; Ulrich et al., 1991; see also Hartig, 2004; von Lindern et al., 2017).

3.3.2 Mechanism: Sleep

Sleep is a biological imperative and affects vital physiological processes and cognitive formation. Although, the detailed function of sleep is not fully clarified, in a broad sense, it serves recuperation and provides the ground for daytime alertness, mental and physical health.

Sleep and sleep structure changes with age, with very young children's sleep having a longer sleep duration (Ohayon et al., 2004). Adolescents generally have sleep need than younger children, however enough sleep is needed for the growth and development of brain and bodies (Carskadon 1990; Dahl & Lewin 2002). Furthermore, several factors related to the transition from childhood to adolescence such as earlier school start time, pubertal phase delay, staying connected (smart phone usage) increase the risk for short sleep duration. The change in sleep physiology (i.e. sleep duration, delay in bedtime, rise time, week vs weekend) is particularly marked from early puberty to late puberty (Dahl & Lewin, 2002; Millman, 2005).

Sleep disturbances could be further divided into: **measures of sleep quantity and sleep pattern; measures of sleep quality; sleep related outcomes** (short term); **sleep related behaviour** and **time** of sleeping during day. Sleep can be measured both subjectively (e.g. through questionnaires and sleep diaries) and objectively (e.g. through polysomnography and actigraphy). The golden standard for measuring sleep and sleep structures is polysomnography (PSG) and involves the recording of the surface electroencephalography (EEG), electrooculogram (EOG) and submental electromyogram (EMG); while actigraphy uses accelerometers to measure motor activity and is used as proxy for some sleep information.

Sleep quantity and pattern could include measures of waking up after asleep onset, arousal, sleep latency and sleep duration. Sleep quality include measures of time to fall asleep, restorative properties of sleep, night waking and bedtime resistance. Sleep related outcomes include insomnia, parasomnia, fatigue, mood and emotional control. Sleep related behaviours include performance, tiredness, mood and irritation during the day. The timing of sleep activity could be measured at night, overnight, evenings or mornings, as well as nocturnal or circadian rhythm.

Adolescent sleep deprivation has been linked to perceived mental health, poor life satisfaction, problems at school and poor grades (Roberts et al. 2009), while short and poor sleep has been shown to be associated with increased risk for depression (Raniti et al 2017). Undisturbed sleep is essential for children's growth and cognitive development (van Kamp et al 2015). A general finding is that short and/or low-quality sleep negatively impacts on children's daytime functioning. Vriend et al (2012) found that poor sleep in the developing child was related to increased negative affect and impaired attention. It has also been suggested that executive functioning effects of sleep deprivation may be particularly serious due to brain development in adolescence during which sensation-seeking is enhanced, and decision-making impaired (Kelley et al. 2004; Steinberg 2004). Sleep is also of high importance for alertness and memory consolidation (Stickgold 2005; Rasch and Born, 2013) and synaptic homeostasis (Tononi et al., 2006). The effect of hormone secretion is closely related to the specific stages of sleep (Van Cauter, 2005). Further, several of the neurotransmitter systems that regulate sleep are responsible also for other functions relevant to psychiatric disorders. It

is therefore plausible that important interactions could occur between sleep and mental disorders. Disturbances of sleep are typical for most depressed patients and sleep disturbance belong to the core symptoms of the disorder (Riemann et al., 2001).

3.3.3 Mechanism: Self-regulation and coping

In Equal-Life, we will consider self-regulation and coping as potential mechanisms in the relationship between the exposome and mental health, and cognitive development outcomes.

Self-regulation refers to a set of skills involved in the conscious, top-down, goal-directed modulation of thought, emotion, and action (Zelazo, 2015). Self-regulation is needed when pursuing short-term goals like staying focused on what the teachers says, but also for achieving complex, long-term goals such as finishing high-school with a good grade. Children's self-regulation is one of the most important predictors of life satisfaction and academic achievement in later years (Zelazo, 2015; Diamond, 2016; Nigg, 2017). However, despite its popularity, there is little agreement on the concepts' definition and scope (Burman, Green, & Shanker, 2015; Nigg, 2017). According to a broad definition proposed by Blair and Diamond (2008), self-regulation *"...refers to the primarily volitional cognitive and behavioural processes through which an individual maintains levels of emotional, motivational, and cognitive arousal that are conducive to positive adjustment and adaptation, as reflected in positive social relationships, productivity, achievement, and a positive sense of self"*. Children's self-regulation skills thus determine the way they react to and manage both daily life challenges, and stressful events.

Evidence from behavioural and neuroimaging studies suggest that self-regulation processes involved in situations that are emotionally and motivationally salient are to some extent dissociable from self-regulation processes involved in cognitive performance in relatively neutral situations, i.e., in laboratory-based, decontextualized tests with little emotional and motivational valence (for reviews, see Nigg, 2017; Zelazo, 2015). The latter are usually referred to as "executive functions" (EFs). EFs play a dominant role in children's cognitive development and academic achievement. In Equal-Life, we will follow this distinction, in that EFs are considered as cognitive outcomes and the term self-regulation is used for control and regulation of one's emotional states.

Emotion-related self-regulation (in the following: emotion regulation) has been defined as *"a process of initiating, avoiding, inhibiting, maintaining, or modulating the occurrence, form, intensity, or duration of internal feeling states, emotion-related physiological responses, attentional processes, motivational states, and/or the behavioural concomitants of emotion in the service of accomplishing affect-related biological or social adaptation or achieving individual goals"* (Eisenberg & Spinrad, 2004, p. 338). Emotion regulation is a major predictor of mental health in childhood and adolescence. Poor emotion regulation is associated with childhood

aggression, internalizing and externalizing symptoms, depression, anxiety, autism-spectrum disorders, obesity, drug abuse and suicide in youth, and other mental health problems (for reviews, see Röll, Koglin, & Petermann, 2012; Joorman & Stanton, 2016; Nigg, 2017; Sheppes, Juri, & Gross, 2015; Schäfer et al., 2017), and mediates the efficiency of interventions targeting health behaviour change (Hennessy et al., 2020).

Coping has been defined as “*Conscious and volitional efforts to regulate emotion, cognition, behaviour, physiology, and the environment in response to stressful events or circumstances*”, or – from a child development perspective – as “*regulation under stress*” (Compas et al., 2001). Coping thus refers to self-regulation processes that are generated specifically in response to stressful events or circumstances, including regulation of physiology, emotion, motivation, cognition, and action. Therefore, when considering children’s responses to stress, emotion regulation and coping are overlapping constructs. Findings indicate that exposure to multiple risks affects children’s overall styles of coping. When the burden of stress associated with multiple risks consistently overwhelms a child’s coping resources, he or she might lose coping-related self-efficacy (i.e. global beliefs about one’s own ability to manage stressful events), resulting in an increased tendency for threat appraisals, perceptions of uncontrollability (helplessness), and avoidant coping. This, in turn, increases the risk of future unsuccessful coping, resulting in further increases of self-inefficacy and risks of negative developmental outcomes.

3.4 Stakeholder consultations and internal expert discussions

The observations and advises of the Equal-Life External Advisory Committee (EAC) guided the expert consultations and workshops aiming at characterizing the external exposome. A major conceptual and empirical challenge in Equal-Life is the determination of the external (physical and social) exposome characteristics salient to the development of good mental health and fulfilling cognitive capacities in children and youth. At present we simply do not have a well-developed taxonomy or classification of what physical characteristics in combination with social factors are salient for healthy child development.

The task of developing an exposome to assess the mental health/cognitive development among children is generally complicated due to developmental considerations. The effects of specific exposures on cognitive or mental health outcomes differ between developmental phases, e.g. interference with speech perception from noise varies with age of exposure. Sleep quality, one of our critical mediating constructs, is affected by the physical environment and those effects differ by age of exposure. In this view, not only the exposome but also outcome measures must be assessed and prioritized for different ages of the child. This implies that there are two tasks at hand: i) selecting and prioritizing an a-priori subset of physical and social factors, and ii) providing the building blocks for a more comprehensive taxonomy of the external exposome to drive future research. The choice of exposome

constructs to be prioritized should be informed by a convergence between theory, available data, and input from stakeholders' personal experiences.

The choice of metrics depends also on the outcome considered. For instance, in terms of population density and crowding (number of people per dwelling) there is only evidence for an association of the latter with well-being. In the noise field, different metrics are relevant when addressing language acquisition compared to well-being, annoyance or activity disturbance. One criterion for choosing what exposome characteristic to exclude is whether it likely shares an underlying mechanism of impact with another exposome characteristic. Another selection criterion concerns the distance of the exposome characteristic from the child. As shown in previous literature, processes that are closer or in more immediate contact with the child are more powerful than those that are more distal. This association further differs per age group of the child. In order to further discuss these matters three meetings were organised, focusing on:

1. **Understanding the external exposome:** arranged for a subgroup of interdisciplinary experts with the aim of characterising the exposome into a taxonomy.
2. **Enriching the external exposome:** arranged for geospatial experts with the aim of discussing the further development of child-related exposure metrics/indices.
3. **Measuring the external exposome:** arranged broadly for all principal investigators with the aim of making further decisions on which external exposures to be included in the first phase of the analyses.

In these meetings (and related follow-up meetings and discussions), agreements were reached on processes, domains, constructs, and relevant indicators, as briefly outlined below:

- **Domains and main constructs:** The physical exposome were subdivided into (i) outdoor quality, (ii) indoor quality, (iii) built environment (often input for indoor and outdoor quality), (iv) natural environment, and (v) lifestyle (somewhere between the physical and social exposome); while the social exposome was considered as a separate domain and hence not further subdivided. Setting, activity, and age were highlighted, and definitions of terminology were set:
 - **Relevant setting:** prenatal, home, day-care, (pre-)school, recreation, *en route*/during transport
 - **Relevant activity:** transport, learning/work, sleep, recreation, physical activity, social activity.
 - **Relevant age groups:** prenatal, 0-3 years, 3-6 years, 7-12 years, 12-16 years, 16-21 years.
 - **Definitions of terminology:**
 - Domain: a sphere of knowledge, influence, or activity (e.g. urban planning)

- Construct or concept: an idea or an imaginary situation (e.g. green space)
 - Variable: any factor that can be controlled, changed, or measured (e.g. exposure to green space)
 - Indicator: a group of statistical values that taken together give an indication of a particular variable (e.g. time spent in green space)
 - Metric: specific instrument/standard of measurement (e.g. number of hours spent in green space within 60 meters from home)
- **Selection criteria:** variables should be given priority/be included on the sake of eight criteria
1. Theoretically feasible
 2. Linking to the key mechanisms of stress, sleep and self-regulation
 3. Confirmed in literature reviews
 4. Positive as well as negative factors and increasing/decreasing resilience
 5. Take distance to the child into account (the closer the better)
 6. Relevant at which developmental phase and during which activities/settings?
 7. Data already available in cohorts and school studies
 8. Data available for enrichment
- **Process:** stepwise selection of variables from the different constructs of the external exposome and the subconstructs physical and social exposome and the cross-cutting fields such as lifestyle, while taking the child, the child's location and the proximity as a point of departure; and reasoning from mental health/cognitive development towards exposures.
- **Data mapping/collection:** protocols for collecting details regarding exposure data available in the cohorts and school studies, and for collecting sources potentially relevant for data enrichment, were developed.
- **Short-listed variables:** Based on the discussions, a list of initially relevant exposure variables was composed per domain and provided with definitions. This list was further rated by mental health and child development experts on relevance and age group, while also taking the selection criteria into consideration, and thereby further refined into a shortlist of relevant key exposures. The short list is presented in Chapter 4.

The stakeholder consultations and internal expert discussions took place also within two sets of Delphi consultations: internal and external. The 'internal' Delphi aimed to harvest ideas and generate early discussion and inputs from Equal-Life researchers and advisory committee for the topics of interest to Equal-Life. As a result of these discussions, 66 questions were proposed as possible questions of interest to the project and rated on relevance and testability within the consortium (Benz, 2020). The results of this internal Delphi informed the overarching research questions list of Equal-Life (Annex 9). The 'external' Delphi collected

information about the needs that the stakeholders are facing in relation to children's and adolescent mental health and cognitive development. The results of the external Delphi guided the research formulation process by providing insight on what stakeholders advise us to do research on (van den Hazel, 2020).

3.5 Defining the exposures relevant for Equal-Life

At an early phase of the project the distinction was made between the internal and external exposome (further divided in physical and social exposome), as shown in Figure 1 above. Below a summary is given of the internal, physical and social exposome concepts relevant for Equal-Life.

3.5.1 The internal exposome

The internal exposome comprises several **internal processes** including metabolism, inflammation, and oxidative stress. While these processes occur in normal physiology, they are also modifiable and capable of altering bodily functions. For example, exposure to environmental toxicants can lead to changes in gene expression due to epigenetic modifications. The internal processes are intrinsically linked to the action of biological molecules such as lipids or other small biomolecules, proteins, genes, or gene regulatory elements. Subsequently, several types of proteins and molecules are present in human blood samples, and some of them have been shown to be associated with psychiatric disorders (Sethi & Brietzke, 2015).

In general, a biomarker is a versatile tool that can for example refer to inflammatory proteins, methylated DNA, and metabolites (Vineis et al., 2020). Biomarkers are widely defined as any substance, structure, or process that can be measured in the body or its products and influence or predict the incidence of outcome or disease (World Health Organization, 2001). The difference between biomarkers and clinical outcome assessments (COAs) is important. COAs measure outcomes that are directly important to the patients and can be used to meet standards for regulatory approval of therapeutics, whereas biomarkers serve a variety of purposes, one of which is to link measurement to a prediction of COAs (Califf, 2018). Biomarkers and omics technologies may allow better causal attribution between the health effect and environmental exposures, for example using instrumental variables in triangulation.

Omics technologies (for example transcriptomic, epigenomic, and proteomic) provide a detailed picture of human bodily function under the influence of environmental exposures and can reveal early mechanistic links with potential health-harming effects (Lan et al. 2004; Smith et al., 2005). Exposomes have been studied earlier in the **EXPOsOMICS** consortium,

which was a project funded by the EU that aims to develop a novel approach for the assessment of exposures to high priority environmental pollutants. Furthermore, the EXPOsOMICS project advanced omics technologies (metabolomics, adductomics) to identify and quantify environmental exposure and applied technologies to measure the downstream effects of **environmental exposures** (epigenome, transcripts, miRNA, proteins). Also, metabolomics studies have been linked to the exposome studies in recent years. In these studies, metabolites are detected as biomarkers that can be affected by environmental exposures, and that are related to inflammation, oxidative stress, and various metabolic pathways (Vineis et al., 2017). Current developments in metabolomics support the detection of molecules related to endogenous processes and metabolism, as well as exogenous compounds (Vineis et al., 2020). New sensitive high-resolution mass spectrometers and the advancement in computational methods for data processing make it possible to analyse over 100,000 molecules in a single sample (Walker et al., 2019). Only the annotation process of data interpretation can limit the development of metabolomics studies (Vineis et al., 2020). An overview of the internal exposome is presented in **Table 1**.

Primary level	Pathway, process, or technique level	Measured component/variation level
Internal processes	Metabolism, inflammation, oxidative stress	Lipids or other small biomolecules
		Proteins
		Genes
		Gene regulatory elements
		Mitochondrial alterations
		Protein-based alterations
		Metabolomics-based alterations
Environmental exposures	Biomarkers	Inflammatory proteins
		Methylated DNA
		Metabolites
Omics technologies	Transcriptomic	Transcripts
	Epigenomic	Epigenetic markers
	Proteomic	Proteins
EXPOsOMICS project	Metabolomics, adductomics	Metabolites
		DNA adducts
		Epigenomes
		Transcripts
		miRNAs

Since the completion of the definition document, selected biomarkers from several cohorts have been analysed in groups with contrasting scores in the total score of SDQ and of the MPNI scales (Whipp et al, Sci Rep 2021). Since the completion of the definition document, selected biomarkers from several cohorts have been analysed in groups with contrasting scores in the total score of SDQ and of the MPNI scales (Whipp et al., 2021). The biomarkers

significantly associated with mental health (assessed by SDQ-scores/p-factor) will be linked with the external exposome and thereafter exposome-biomarker associations will be explored.

3.5.2 The external exposome: physical exposome

In Equal-Life we refer to **external exposome** as the umbrella term for all environmental exposures of an individual caused by the collective action of other persons and/or natural phenomena. In this definition, external exposome is directly related to the description of the *state* of the environment² but the spatiotemporal granularity will be finer than usual in environmental studies.

In the Equal-Life proposal, external physical exposome is further subdivided in five categories:

1. **The outdoor environmental quality:** e.g. noise and sound quality, air quality, housing practices.
2. **The indoor environmental quality:** e.g. mother smoking during pregnancy, child passive smoking, crowding, indoor air quality, indoor sound quality, household chemicals, prenatal chemicals.
3. **The built environment:** e.g. level of urbanization, type of neighbourhood, street connectivity, junctions' density, road types, land-use, building quality (housing quality, age of building), crowding, physical safety, walkability, access to facilities such as playground, sportsground, parks, culture and relevant moderators such as length of residency.
4. **The natural environment:** e.g. green space, blue space, access to green and blue space (residential/school/on the move), playability, biodiversity, safety, activities in green and blue spaces.
5. **Lifestyle factors:** e.g. sleep (duration/quality/rhythm), substance use, healthy food intake, activity patterns, mobility/mode of commuting, leisure time, sports, sunlight exposure, playtime online.

This subdivision not only refers to different micro-environments but also to different **levels of abstraction** and **spatiotemporal granularity**. Exposures at higher levels of abstraction (e.g. yearly average equivalent noise levels at street level) combined with low granularity (e.g. noise level measurements at the façade of a building without considering the building material, its position towards streets, etc.) may be easier to assess and could show strong statistical power on the target outcomes. Lower levels of abstraction could emerge as scientific knowledge grows and may be more suited for guiding policy. Hence Equal-Life will

² Here, *state* is used as defined in the classical DPSIR (driving forces – pressure – state – impact – response) environmental chain of indicators.

push to the lowest possible level of abstraction and the highest possible spatiotemporal granularity that could still be obtained at an acceptable effort/cost.

3.5.2.1 Activity pattern/space as a context

Exposure depends on activity pattern and the space where the activity takes place, as well as the time of day and season. Activity determines susceptibility to environmental factors (e.g. noise during sleep) and which micro-environments are visited (e.g. public transport, school). Hence Equal-Life aims to move from describing exposure by administrative boundaries to actual used space. This may be particularly relevant as activity space increases with age. But it could also increase with social status (car use, possibly bringing children to “better” schools further away, etc.). Activity pattern and activity space can therefore provide a strong link between the physical exposome, social exposome and mental health and cognitive effects.

Activity pattern/space of children will be measured and subsequently be modelled as a function of age group, social status, and characteristics of the built environment (e.g. density of schools and recreational facilities). Making this differentiation in activity pattern/space we can see what micro-environments/settings are relevant for children within specific age and/or social groups. These differences in micro-environments/settings are the key to differences in environmental exposure and therefore health effects. Following the definitions of Bronfenbrenner (1979), it is important to note that a micro-environment is not a causal consequence of a sequence of locations, activities and social interactions but is rather an experience of a given setting with specific physical and material characteristics. Different settings (a place where people can interact) may give rise to different patterns of roles, activities, and social relations, which are also affected by “higher level” factors such as cultural background.

3.5.2.2 Social and physical setting and age-specific effects

The effect of the exposome may differ strongly over the different development phases of the child (Lipina, 2016; Schoon, 2002). In the grant proposal this was illustrated by **Figure 6a-b**, presented below. The terminology has since then been revised, as presented throughout this document.

Figure 6a. Selected social aspects and the effect of the exposome across different developmental stages.

Figure 6b. The physical exposome and the effect of the exposome across different developmental stages.

The factor of age in exposome takes different forms:

- The **activities** change over time which implies the use of different micro-environments and consequently different exposures.
- Due to the **developing brain**, the child may also be much more vulnerable to specific exposures at different life stages.
- Early exposure may increase **sensitivity** (e.g. through changes in epigenetic regulation) for environmental factors or may enhance resilience. This is one way of how exposome is connected over the lifetime of a child.

3.5.3 The external exposome: social exposome

Based on an extensive literature review a theoretical framework was developed (see paper on the concept of the social exposome in the upcoming special issue in Environmental Research) that helps to explain how children's social environment, socioeconomic circumstances, and societal context impacts their mental health, cognitive development, and well-being. We define the social environment as the complex and dynamic interplay of different individual- and societal-level factors.

The social exposome can be broadly understood as the entirety of the *social environment* and incorporates so-called *social exposures*. We define the social environment as the complex and dynamic interplay of social and psychosocial aspects, which also incorporates the broader societal context as well as community- and individual-level factors, including socioeconomic and sociodemographic aspects relevant to understanding structural social inequalities. Further details on the dimensions and components of the social exposome are given in the specific paper on the concept of the social exposome in the upcoming special issue in Environmental Research.

The individual-level factors include:

- **Actors:** the persons that the child interacts with such as family, peers, companions, official figures, other adult figures, acquaintances and digital contacts.
- **Relational dynamics:** the nature of interactions between the individual and their interaction partners, e.g. the level of social support the child receives from their parents.
- **Places:** the location the social interactions occur such as home, places for leisure time, places for learning, workplaces, the digital world and the neighbourhood composed of the social and physical environment.

Within the framework of the social exposome, the broader context that an individual and their social interactions is embedded in is represented by interlinked dimensions:

Socioeconomic circumstances and sociodemographic characteristics, systems, institutions and priorities of the political economy, and the overarching "cognitive" structures of **social**

norms and cultural values. All elements within the social exposome are assumed to be interlinked and together influence social inequalities in the exposome and in health.

- **Socioeconomic circumstances and sociodemographic characteristics:** describe living conditions and attributes of a person at a certain point in time.
- **Social inequalities and structural injustices:** representing the laws, rules and regulations that are social determinants of living and working conditions
- **Social norms and cultural values:** Legal and non-legal social norms operate to guide standards or expectations of behaviour, especially in social settings. Cultural values, in a similar way to social norms, represent the underlying assumptions and beliefs. Different cultural values and different prioritisation of these cultural values – as well as opportunities to realise them – can be the basis for potential discrimination alongside also norms that can act to privilege or disadvantage particular groups
- **Systems, institutions, and priorities of the political economy:** interaction between proposed dimensions especially the socioeconomic circumstances and sociodemographic characteristics, systems, institutions and priorities of the political economy, social norms, and cultural values. Social inequalities in health are driven by the political, socio-cultural and economic forces that ultimately determine the inequities in the circumstances in which people grow, live, work, and age.

4. Final selection of the external exposome ³

4.1 Shortlist of key exposure variables

The shortlist of variables stemming from discussions and ratings (as described in section 3.4) is an overview of the variables with most relevancy/importance for Equal-Life. This list is presented in **Table 2**. In the table, variables with high relevance/importance are represented by green colouring (average rating ≥ 4), moderate relevance by yellow colouring (average rating between 3 and 4), and low relevance by red colouring (average rating < 3). Annex 7 presents the shortlisted variable list with their definitions, and Annex 8 presents the variables which were rejected (marked as red) for the shortlist.

³ For an update we refer to D7.2 and D7.3

Table 2. Short-listed variables of relevance in Equal-Life
Outdoor Quality
Air quality outdoor Residential /school/preschool
Sound/Noise quality outdoor Residential/school/preschool Outdoor
Outdoor restorative quality
Housing practices
Indoor Quality
Mother smoking during pregnancy
Child passive smoking
Indoor environmental quality at home/school/preschool (mould/dust/dampness/overall)
Crowding Residential, Preschool and school
Indoor Air quality, NO ₂ (as proxy for traffic related air pollution), particulate matter
Indoor Sound, quality
Home toxics/Household chemicals
Prenatal: Mother work chemicals/household chemicals
Built environment
Density (population, building, activities, distribution of functions)
Amenity (sidewalks, bike-paths, parks, libraries, playgrounds, sport facilities, health food /health care)
Street integration and connectivity
Access to healthy food
Public transport lines
Walkability
Natural Environment
Access to green space (residential. Preschool, school, "en route")
Access to blue space (residential. Preschool, school, "en route")
Playability
Safety related to playability
Safety green and blue space
Activities green/blue space
Lifestyle
Sleep (duration, quality, rhythm)
Smoking
Substance use
Food: healthy food intake, breast feeding
Activity patterns
Mobility/mode of commuting
Leisure time
Sports
Sunlight exposure
Playtime Online, Playing Videogames (social media use), Blue light TV watching
Social environment
Work and income situation, educational background, individual, household, neighbourhood level.
Social interaction
Social integration/cohesion/network (e.g. neighbourhood, preschool, school)
Stressful life events
Parenting style and quality and practices

Parental depression/anxiety
Chaotic living conditions
Family instability
Support from parents
Violence/maltreatment
Caring and household responsibilities
Academic stress (child)
Home learning environment
Resilience/susceptibility (physical/social)
Quality of school/teaching
Experiences of discrimination (e.g. as a result of sex/gender, sexuality, ethnicity, religious affiliation).
Social modelling
Sex/gender, age, religion, household structure, migration background
Age of the parents
Average rating ≥ 4
Average rating between 3 and 4

The shortlisted variables were taken as a point of departure by the data enrichers, for selection, and subsequent development and operationalisation, of indicators; as well as for further prioritization, specification and operationalisation of the research questions of relevance in Equal-Life (see sections below). The short-listed variables in a sense served as a theoretical “wish”-list, highlighting the most relevant variables for the outcomes under study in Equal-Life. Hence, the list serves as a basis for prioritization of available exposures, enrichment, and the operationalisation of the multimodal exposome in connection with the research questions of interest in Equal-Life.

4.2 Data mapping and data harmonisation

Within the project, a large amount of data was already available from the included cohorts and school studies – all with various study design, age range and time periods in which the data was collected (see Van Kamp et al., 2022 for a more detailed method description). In order to make the information from these data sets available for harmonisation and operationalisation, a searchable database was created. This database also served as a guide for the enrichment process. To retrieve details on the data available, we collected information from the cohorts which included questionnaires used in the studies, data codebooks, previous papers published from the cohorts, and we held one-to-one meetings with the cohort owners. These sources were brought together to map out the available data in the database. The structure of the data base was guided by the suggestions made during the expert meetings and discussions, and by the concepts and sub-concepts defined in the definition documents (as described in previous sections). **Figure 7** visualises the design and content of the data base.

Cohort	Main-concept	Sub-concept	Metric/Indicator	Instrument/Data Source	Person/unit of interest	Age of child at measurement	Available sample	Reference	Notes
STARS	Education	School attendance	Two-Item measure of skipping school and habit of being late to school (5 answers: no, yes sometime per school term, yes sometime per month, yes several times per month, yes several times per week)	STARS Child Questionnaire	child	13 years old	2283		
FINNTWIN	Education	Unannounced absence	%absence	School records	child	13 years old	2283		
FINNTWIN	Education	School attendance	Are you presently attending school? 3 categories (Don't go to school nor study, go to school or study but don't work; go to school or study and work for n hours/week)	Child's questionnaire	child	17	4236		
ABCD	Education	Unannounced absence	In which class is the pupil currently?	Teacher's questionnaire	child	11-12	2034		
ABCD	Education	Current education	How many days in the past year did you stay home from school because you were sick? How many days in the past 4 school weeks did you arrive late at school because of troubles getting up or didn't feel well in the morning?	Child's questionnaire	child	15-16	2200		
ABCD	Education	Homework	How many hours per week do you spend on homework?	Child's questionnaire	child	15-16	2200		

Figure 7. Visualisation of the design and content of the database containing available data for further use in Equal-life.

4.3 Enrichment of exposures

Following the identification of relevant constructs in the context of children’s mental health and cognitive development, and the collection of potential national/regional data sources and geocoordinates to be used in the enrichment process, a number of variables have been developed with the purpose of enriching the already available data in Equal-life and facilitating the operationalisation of the multimodal exposome. In the context of this deliverable, it is important to note that, apart from conceptual, theoretical and scientific arguments, the choice of research questions also guided the description of the requirements for data enrichment.

The knowledge gained by understanding the requirements for the data enrichment informed the enrichment task which was carried out by: identifying relevant data sets and defining the focus areas for enrichment; calculating the properties of the natural and built environment relevant for the physical exposome; designing and creating the required methods and tools for creation and enrichment; and identifying the crowd contributors needed to provide information on human perception of their environment. Together, these enrichment tasks lead up to the operationalisation of the multimodal exposome.

In terms of the built and natural environment, a number of variables have been or are being explored and developed, such as:

- Street network morphological and topological characteristics, i.e. betweenness centrality, intersection closeness centrality, sinuosity
- Elements of street infrastructure, i.e. sidewalks, bike paths

- Access to urban green spaces and other amenities with accessibility metrics, i.e. pedestrian walksheds, on-the-move accessibility, co-accessibility
- Safety along streets, i.e. natural surveillance
- Urbanization levels, i.e. population density, building density, imperviousness (grey space), land use, roads and connectivity, accessibility to public transport
- Natural spaces, i.e., blue and green spaces (distance, size and accessibility), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI), Vegetation Continuous Fields (VCF).

4.3.1 Enrichment of built environment: co-accessibility

The lack of mutual encounters and interactions between different population groups can lead to an increased feeling of segregation and, thereby, jeopardize the goal of accessible and inclusive public spaces, with negative effects on mental health in the long run. This phenomenon is often referred to as spatial age segregation. Common indicators of spatial age segregation that have extensively been used in literature are the concentration and distribution of different population age groups residing within a neighborhood. Yet people may further experience age segregation in places outside of the residential space. So, what if we look at segregation not only in relation to where people live, but also in terms of how *accessible* different activity spaces are to different population groups?

In the context of Equal-Life, we propose a radically new approach to measuring age segregation in our daily activity spaces. Besides looking at how accessible different activity spaces are, we also consider how likely it is that people from different groups meet in these places. For this, we introduce a spatial “co-accessibility” index, as part of the built-environment enrichments within Equal-Life. Unlike typical determinants of spatial accessibility (i.e., the distance between an origin (usually the home location) and a destination, travel time, and associated costs), we further consider the spatial distribution of different destinations (e.g., greenspaces, playgrounds) and the age diversity of people who potentially occupy these places at the same time. The estimated age-adjusted co-accessibility metrics enable us to identify to what degree each amenity is accessible to different age groups. Related enrichments and analyses within Equal-Life suggest that the likelihood of an individual to be exposed to people from different age groups when visiting a greenspace or a playground is influenced by the location of these places, the distribution density, and the time required to reach them (i.e., destinations within a 10 or 15-minute walk from a person’s home yield higher age diversity scores, relative to destinations within a 5-minute walk). Detailed analyses and enrichment results have been documented in (Miliadis & Psyllidis, 2022).

Figure 8. Activity locations across the five most-populated Dutch cities, classified according to the percentage of children and the elderly that can access each location relative to all the other groups within two different walking distances (5 and 15-min walksheds).

4.3.2 Enrichment of natural environment: vegetation indices

Among other natural environment indicators, within the Equal-Life project, the green space indicators Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI) and Vegetation Continuous Fields (VCF) are being derived using satellite data and geo-coordinates (of addresses of home, schools and/or day care centers of children included in the cohorts in Equal-Life) collected from the cohorts.

From the different satellites deriving vegetation indices it was decided to use Landsat due to:

- Free and available.
- Wide temporal coverage as it provides data from 1982 so it covers all study periods.
- Good spatial resolution as it is 30m * 30m.

For MSAVI and NDVI analysis, the imagery had been selected according to the following criteria using the Google Earth Engine:

1. Select images available from the level 2 data, Tier 1 and with the Surface Reflectance correction done.
2. Subset images between the spring and summer seasons as identified as the greenest season between the years of interest.
3. Remove pixels identified as clouds, snow and water.

4.3.2.1 NDVI

NDVI quantifies vegetation by measuring the difference between near-infrared (NIR), which vegetation strongly reflects, and red light, which vegetation absorbs. NDVI values range from +1 to -1 where areas of barren rock, sand, or snow usually show very low NDVI with values around 0.1; sparse vegetation such as shrubs and grasslands or senescing crops may result in moderate NDVI with values approximately between 0.2 to 0.5; dense vegetation such as tropical forests or crops at their peak growth stage high NDVI with values approximately between 0.6 to 0.9. Negative values of NDVI approaching to -1 correspond to water.

NDVI is calculated using the following formula:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red}$$

Figure 9. Two NDVI scenes for Barcelona city area for year 2000 and 2020 which captures the differences across time on greening infrastructures.

4.3.2.2 MSAVI

MSAVI minimizes the effect of bare soil on the Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI). MSAVI is calculated as a ratio between the Red and Near Infrared (NIR) values with a correction to maximize the reduction of soil effects on the vegetation signal. MSAVI is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{MSAVI} = \frac{2*(NIR+1) - \sqrt{(2*NIR+1)^2 - 8*(NIR - Red)}}{2}$$

4.3.2.3 VCF

VCF identifies the percentage of tree cover which may have a different role in health than other green indices such as NDVI or MSAVI. In Equal-Life, we will therefore derive the amount of area covered by trees around a geocode using the product of Global Forest Cover Change (GFCC) which is a dataset on tree cover available at four years period: 2000, 2005, 2010 and 2015. GFCC is derived from the Global Land Survey (GLS) datasets which are available on Landat 5 and 7 missions with a 30 m resolution.

4.3.3 Enrichment of the social exposome

Based on the newly developed concept of the social exposome, a shortlist of twenty social indicators has been created. These indicators reflect the different dimensions of the social exposome. Furthermore, an essential criterion was to find indicators that are available (e.g. identified in national statistical bureaus) in several, ideally in all, Equal-Life cohort countries on a municipality level. Social enrichment will be aligned to time periods of data collection of the particular cohort to complement individual-level data.

4.4 Operationalising the multimodal exposome

Within Equal-Life, relevant research questions were developed and formulated in parallel with a series of tasks including literature reviews, theoretical frameworks, definition documents, short-listing of variables, and discussions on the relevancy of the exposome for the outcomes of interest. Here, the data base exercise served as anchor points for the formulation of overarching research questions, especially concerning the outcomes and mechanisms. Non-targeted analyses in a selection of the datasets were also used to further refine the research questions, as they provided some guidance on which exposures deemed especially relevant for the specific outcomes. A yet generic, but inclusive, list of research questions was created based on these interrelated tasks, in part focusing on the *mechanisms* by which exposures can put children at risk or promote mental health and cognitive development (“how”-questions), and in part focusing on the *exposures* per se, in residential, pre-school and school settings, and the association with the selected outcomes (“which”-questions). The research questions also grapple at the construction of the exposome, being cumulative, age-stage specific, or based on the irregularity, unpredictability, and duration of exposures on the outcomes, see Annex 9.

Operationalising the exposome within the frames of the specific research questions is an ongoing process. Much of this work is currently carried out in teams formed around the specific outcomes (cognitive development; internalizing/externalizing symptoms and behaviour; well-being; mental health diagnoses) and also around the mechanisms. The teams

are working with variable selection, operationalisation, as well as further hypotheses formulation and creation of detailed plans of analysis.

5. Conclusions and a way ahead

5.1 Summary

The aim of this document is to provide an overview of the requirements for the multimodal data collection pertaining to enrichment of data, with emphasis on the natural and built environment, but not excluding the other domains of enrichment. It is based on literature reviews and stakeholder consultations, but most of all expert-based discussions and working sessions. The definition documents set up by experts within the field, helped select the outcomes to focus on. When the outcomes were decided, a more targeted selection and prioritization of the exposome variables could be made. This was done by several discussions, working sessions and rating tasks. The end result is a short list of key exposure variables, which is currently being used by the data enrichers to construct enriched exposome variables and is being used by the teams preparing the analyses for cognitive development, internalizing/externalizing symptoms and behaviour, well-being, and mental health diagnoses. In order to help the prioritisation of the shortlist further, a mapping, grouping and harmonisation of the existing variables in the cohort has been made. There is no need for enrichment of variables that have already been assessed in a sufficient way.

5.2 Strengths and weaknesses

In an exposome project with multiple exposures and multiple outcomes, finding the key variables and thereby the focus of the project is many times difficult. In particular, since the exposome field is new and the mental health and cognitive development outcomes are less studied in association with the exposome. In addition, we are aware that in this selection process we miss out on potentially relevant exposures. However, this also allows us to focus or effort on key exposures not fully studied until now.

The strong points of this approach are the theory and expertise-based and stakeholder-based consultations as well as expert based ranking rounds, aiming for consensus about the relevant exposures. The outcome-oriented approach rather than randomly and in an agnostic way including exposures, enable us to further the field instead of limiting ourselves in a non-targeted approach.

5.3 Where we stand now and the way ahead

We have a useable list of relevant exposures to make a start with data enrichment and data analyses. In the course of the project, new variables can be added to this list. Further decisions to be made with the regard to the health effect analyses ahead include us to elaborate on relevance per age phase, single versus accumulated and composite indicators and prioritizing within social and physical exposures, as well as looking into the interplay of both. Another challenge is the interrelations and the accumulation of exposures in deprived neighbourhoods as well as how to Include time activity patterns. A further focus area is how to link the exposures an outcome to underlying mechanisms, including the internal exposome. We also should keep in mind that differential exposure to negative and positive environmental characteristics as well as differential vulnerability (or resilience) should also contribute to prioritization of which variables to examine as components of the external exposome.

6. References

- Babisch, W. (2002). The Noise/Stress Concept, Risk Assessment and Research Needs. *Noise & Health*, 4, 1–11.
- Bachman, P. et al., (2012). Processing Speed and Neurodevelopment in Adolescent-Onset Psychosis: Cognitive Slowing Predicts Social Function. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology*, 40:645–654. DOI 10.1007/s10802-011-9592-5
- Benz, S., Belke, C., Riedel, N., Schreckenber, D., Weber, M., van Kamp, I. (2020). Expert Consultation on Research Questions in Equal-Life (Delphi survey). Internal deliverable paper of the Horizon 2020-funded project Equal-Life.
- Blair, C. & Diamond, A. (2008). Biological processes in prevention and intervention: The promotion of self-regulation as a means of preventing school failure. *Development and Psychopathology*, 20(3): 899–911.
- Bodenmann, G. & Gmelch, S. (2009). Stressbewältigung. In J. Margraf & S. Schneider (Hrsg.), *Lehrbuch der Verhaltenstherapie* (S. 617–629). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The Ecology of Human Development*. Harvard University Press.
- Burman, J.; Green, C. & Shanker, S. (2015). On the Meanings of Self-Regulation: Digital Humanities in Service of Conceptual Clarity. *Child Development*, 86, 1507–1521.
- Califf, R. M. 2018. Biomarker definitions and their applications. *Exp Biol Med* (Maywood). 2018 Feb; 243(3): 213–221. doi: 10.1177/1535370217750088
- Carskadon, M. A. (1990). Patterns of sleep and sleepiness in adolescents. *Pediatrician*, 17(1), 5–12.
- Caspi, A., Houts, R. M., Belsky, D. W., Goldman-Mellor, S. J., Harrington, H., Israel, S., . . . Moffitt, T. E. (2014). The p Factor: One General Psychopathology Factor in the Structure of Psychiatric Disorders? *Clin Psychol Sci*, 2(2), 119-137
- Chrousos, G. P. (2009). Stress and disorders of the stress system. *Nat. Rev. Endocrinol.* 5, 374–381. doi:10.1038/nrendo.2009.106.
- Cohen, S., Janicki-Deverts, D. & Miller, G.E. (2007). Psychological stress and disease. (Reprinted) *JAMA*, 298(14), 1685-1687.
- Compas, B. E., Connor-Smith, J. K., Saltzman, H., Thomsen, A. H., & Wadsworth, M. E. (2001). Coping with stress during childhood and adolescence: Problems, progress, and potential in theory and research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 127(1), 87–127. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0033-2909.127.1.87>

Council of Europe. (2018). Council recommendation on key competences for lifelong learning. Official Journal of the European Union, 61(C 189).

Dahl, R. E., & Lewin, D. S. (2002). Pathways to adolescent health: Sleep regulation and behavior. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 31(6), 175–184

Dhakal A, Bobrin BD. Cognitive Deficits. 2022 Jun 27. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan–. PMID: 32644478.

Diamond, A. (2016). Why improving and assessing executive functions early in life is critical. In: Griffin, J.; McCardle, P.; & Freund, L. (Eds.). *Executive Functions in Preschool-Age children*. pp. 11-43. APA. doi:10.1146/annurev-psych-113011-143750.

Eisenberg, N., & Spinrad, T. L. (2004). Emotion-related regulation: Sharpening the definition. *Child Development*, 75, 334–339.

Goodman, A., & Goodman, R. (2009). Strengths and difficulties questionnaire as a dimensional measure of child mental health. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 48, 400-403

Han, K. T. (2003). A Reliable and Valid Self-rating Measure of the Restorative Quality of Natural Environments. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 64(4), 209–232.

Hartig, T. (2004). Restorative environments. In C. Spielberger (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of applied psychology* (pp. 273–279). San Diego: Academic.

Hartig, T. (2007). Three steps to understanding restorative environments as health resources. In C. Ward Thompson & P. Travlou (Eds.), *Open space: People space* (pp. 163-179). London: Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203961827-22>

Hartig, T. (2016). Restorative effects of nature experience: Theoretical and methodological considerations. Presentation at “Exploring potential pathways linking greenness and green spaces to health: workshop for experts”, Munich-Herrsching, 21.09.2016.

Hennessy, E, A., Blair T., Johnson, R. L., Acabchuk, McCloskey, K. & Stewart-James, J. (2020). Self-Regulation Mechanisms in Health Behavior Change: A Systematic Meta-Review of Meta-Analyses, 2006–2017. *Health Psychology Review* 14 (1): 6–42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17437199.2019.1679654>.

Joormann, J., & Stanton, C. H. (2016). Examining emotion regulation in depression: A review and future directions. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 86, 35–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2016.07.007>

Kail, R. (1991). Developmental change in speed of processing during childhood and adolescence. *Psychological Bulletin*, 109(3), 490–501.

Kail, R.V., Lervåg, A. and Hulme, C. (2016), Longitudinal evidence linking processing speed to the development of reasoning. *Developmental Science*, 19: 1067-1074.

Kaplan, R., & Kaplan, S. (1989). *The experience of nature: A psychological perspective*. New York, Cambridge: University Press.

Kaplan, S., 1995. The restorative benefits of nature: towards an integrative framework. *J. Environ. Psychol.* 15, 169–182.

Kelly, W. E. (2004). Sleep-length and life satisfaction in a college student sample. *College Student Journal*, 38(3), 428–430.

Keyes, C. (2007). Promoting and protecting mental health as flourishing: a complementary strategy for improving national mental health. *The American Psychologist*, 62(2), 95-108

Koolhaas, J.M., Bartolomucci, A., Buwalda, B., Boer, S.F. de, Flügge, G., Korte, S.M. et al. (2011). Stress revisited: A critical evaluation of the stress concept. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews*, 35, 1291–1301.

Lahey, B. B., Zald, D. H., Perkins, S. F., Villalta-Gil, V., Werts, K. B., Van Hulle, C. A., . . . Waldman, I. D. (2018). Measuring the hierarchical general factor model of psychopathology in young adults. *International Journal of Methods in Psychiatric Research*, 27(1)

Lan, Q., Zhang, L., Li, G., Vermeulen, R., Weinberg, R. S., Dosemeci, M., Rappaport, S. M., Shen, M., Alter, B. P., Wu, Y., Kopp, W., Waidyanatha, S., Rabkin, C., Guo, W., Chanock, S., Hayes, R. B., Linet, M., Kim, S., Yin, S., Rothman, N. & Smith, M. T. 2005. Hematotoxicity in Workers Exposed to Low Levels of Benzene. *Science: Vol. 306, Issue 5702*, pp. 1774-1776. DOI: 10.1126/science.1102443

Lipina, S.J. The biological side of social determinants: Neural costs of childhood poverty. *Prospects* 46, 265–280 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-017-9390-0>

Malekinezhad, F. & Bin Lamit, H. (2018). Restoration Experience Measurement Methods in Contact with Green Open Spaces. *Preprints 2018*, 2018010064 (doi: 10.20944/preprints201801.0064.v1)

Masten, A. S., & Curtis, W. J. (2000). Integrating competence and psychopathology: pathways toward a comprehensive science of adaptation in development. *Development and Psychopathology*, 12(3), 529-550.

Miles, J., Espiritu, R. C., Horen, N., Sebian, J., & Waetzig, E. (2010). *A Public Health. Approach to Children's Mental Health: A Conceptual Framework*. Georgetown, Washington D.C. : Georgetown University Center for Child and Human Development, National Technical Assistance Center for Children's Mental Health.

Milias, V. & Psyllidis, A. Measuring spatial age segregation through the lens of co-accessibility to urban activities. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems* Jul 2022; DOI:10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2022.101829.

Millman R. P Excessive Sleepiness in Adolescents and Young Adults: Causes, Consequences, and Treatment Strategies. *Pediatrics* Jun 2005, 115 (6) 1774-1786; DOI: 10.1542/peds.2005-0772

Moll, K.; Göbel, S, Gooch, D.; Landerl, K. & Snowling, M. (2016). Cognitive Risk Factors for Specific Learning Disorder: Processing Speed, Temporal Processing, and Working Memory. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*,49(3), 272–281.

Neisser, U. (1967). *Cognitive psychology*. New York: Appelton-Century-Crofts.

Nigg, J. (2017). Annual Research Review: On the relations among self-regulation, self-control, executive functioning, effortful control, cognitive control, impulsivity, risk-taking, and inhibition for developmental psychopathology. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 58:4, 361–383.

O'Connor, E., O'Connor, M., Gray, S., & Goldfeld, S. (2018). Profiles of mental health competence and difficulties as predictors of children's early learning. *School Mental Health*, 10, 402-416

Office for National Statistics, UK. (2011). *Measuring what matters: National Statistician's Reflections on the National Debate on Measuring National Well-being*. Cardiff, United Kingdom.

Ohayon MM, Carskadon MA, Guilleminault C, Vitiello MV. Meta-analysis of quantitative sleep parameters from childhood to old age in healthy individuals: developing normative sleep values across the human lifespan. *Sleep*. 2004;27(7):1255-1273. doi:10.1093/sleep/27.7.

Pettersson, E., Lahey, B. B., Larsson, H., & Lichtenstein, P. (2018). Criterion Validity and Utility of the General Factor of Psychopathology in Childhood: Predictive Associations With Independently Measured Severe Adverse Mental Health Outcomes in Adolescence. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 57(6), 372-383

Raniti MB, Allen NB, Schwartz O, Waloszek JM, Byrne ML, Woods MJ, et al. Sleep Duration and Sleep Quality: Associations With Depressive Symptoms Across Adolescence. *Behavioral Sleep Medicine*. 2017;15(3):198-215.

Rasch, B., and Born, J. (2013). About Sleep's Role in Memory. *Physiol Rev* 93(2), 681-766.

Ravens-Sieberer, U., Karow, A., Barthel, D., & Klasen, F. (2014). How to assess quality of life in child and adolescent psychiatry. *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, 16(2), 147-158

Riedel, N., van Kamp, I., Köckler, H., Scheiner, J., Loerbroks, A., Claßen, T. & Bolte, G. (2017). Cognitive-Motivational Determinants of Residents' Civic Engagement and Health (Inequities)

in the Context of Noise Action Planning: A Conceptual Model. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14, 578.

Riemann D, Berger M, Voderholzer U. Sleep and depression — results from psychobiological studies: an overview. *Biol Psychol* 2001;57:67-103. [PubMed]

Riglin, L., Thapar, A. K., Leppert, B., Martin, J., Richards, A., Anney, R., . . . Thapar, A. (2019). Using Genetics to Examine a General Liability to Childhood Psychopathology. *Behavior Genetics*

Röll J, Koglin U, Petermann F. (2012). Emotion regulation and childhood aggression: longitudinal associations. *Child Psychiatry and Human Development*, 43(6):909-923. doi:10.1007/s10578-012-0303-4

Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2001). On happiness and human potentials: a review of research on hedonic and eudaimonic well-being. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52, 141-166.

Schäfer, J. Ö., Naumann, E., Holmes, E. A., Tuschen-Caffier, B., & Samson, A. C. (2017). Emotion Regulation Strategies in Depressive and Anxiety Symptoms in Youth: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 46(2), 261–276. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-016-0585-0>

Schoon, I., Bynner, J., Joshi, H., Parsons, S., Wiggins, R. D., & Sacker, A. (2002). The influence of context, timing, and duration of risk experiences for the passage from childhood to midadulthood. *Child development*, 73(5), 1486–1504. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00485>

Selye, H. (1974). *Stress without Distress*. Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott.

Sethi, S. & Brietzke, E. 2016. Omics-Based Biomarkers: Application of Metabolomics in Neuropsychiatric Disorders. *Int J Neuropsychopharmacol*. 2016 Mar; 19(3). doi: 10.1093/ijnp/pyv096

Sheppes, G., Suri, G., & Gross, J. J. (2015). Emotion regulation and psychopathology. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 11, 379–405. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-032814-112739>

Slade, M. (2010). Mental illness and well-being: the central importance of positive psychology and recovery approaches. *BMC Health Services Research*, 26(10), 26

Smith, M. T., Vermeulen, R., Li, G., Zhang, L., Lan, Q., Hubbard, A. E., Forrest, M. S., McHale, C., Zhao, X., Gunn, L., Shen, M., Rappaport, S. M., Yin, S., Chanock, S. & Rothman, N. 2005. Use of 'Omic' technologies to study humans exposed to benzene. *Chemico-Biological Interactions*, 153–154, 30 May 2005, 123-127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2005.03.017>

Steinberg, L. (2004). Risk taking in adolescence. What changes, and why? In R. E. Dahl & L. P. Spear (Eds.), *Adolescent brain development. Vulnerabilities and opportunities* (Vol. 1021, pp. 51–58). New York, NY: New York Academy of Sciences.

Stewart-Brown, S., Tennant, A., Tennant, R., Platt, S., Parkinson, J., & Weich, S. (2009). Internal construct validity of the Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (WEMWBS): a Rasch analysis using data from the Scottish Health Education Population Survey. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 19(7), 15

Stickgold, R. (2005). Sleep-dependent memory consolidation. *Nature* 437(7063), 1272-1278.

Tononi, G., and Cirelli, C. (2006). Sleep function and synaptic homeostasis. *Sleep Med Rev* 10(1), 49-62.

Ulrich, R. S. (1983). Aesthetic and affective response to natural environment. In I. Altman & J. F. Wohlwill (Eds.), *Behavior and the natural environment* (pp. 85–125). New York: Springer.

Ulrich, R. S., Simons, R. F., Losito, B. D., Fiorito, E., Miles, M. A., & Zelson, M. (1991). Stress recovery during exposure to natural and urban environments. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 11(3), 201–230. doi:10.1016/S0272-4944(05)80184-7.

Ursin, H. & Eriksen, H. R. (2004). The cognitive activation theory of stress. *Psychoneuroendocrinology*, 29(5), 567-592.

Van Cauter E. Endocrine physiology. In *Principle and Practise of Sleep Medicine*, 4th edn (Eds Kryger M, Roth T and Dement W.C.)266-282 (Elsevier –Saundes, Philadelphia, 2005).

Van den Hazel, P. (2020). Strategy report on stakeholder identification, interaction and involvement. Deliverable 8.1 within Equal-Life.

Van Kamp I, Persson Waye K, Gunnarsson AG (2015). The Effects of Noise Disturbed Sleep in Children on Cognitive Development and Long Term Health. *J Child Adolesc Behav* 3:179. doi:10.4172/2375-4494.1000179.

Van Kamp, Irene ; Persson Waye, Kerstin; Kanninen, Katja; Gulliver, John; Bozzon, Alessandro; Psyllidis, Achilleas ... Bolte, Gabriele; Equal-Life Scientific Team (2022). Early environmental quality and life-course mental health effects: The Equal-Life project. *Environmental Epidemiology*, 6 (1), p e183 doi: 10.1097/EE9.0000000000000183

Whipp AM, Vuoksima E, Korhonen T, Pool R, But A, Ligthart L, Hagenbeek FA, Bartels M, Bogl LH, Pulkkinen L, Rose RJ, Boomsma DI, Kaprio J (2021). Ketone body 3-hydroxybutyrate as a biomarker of aggression. *Sci Rep.*, 11(1):5813. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-84635-6.

Vineis, P., Chadeau-Hyam, M., Gmuender, H., Gulliver, J., Herceg, Z., Kleinjans, J., Kogevinas, M., e Kyrtopoulos, S., Nieuwenhuijsen, M., Phillips, D. H., Probst-Hensch, N., Scalbert, A., Vermeulen, R., Wild, C. P. & The EXPOsOMICS Consortium. 2017. The exposome in practice:

Design of the EXPOsOMICS project. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2017 Mar; 220(2Part A): 142–151. doi: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2016.08.001

Vineis, P., Robinson, O., Chadeau-Hyam, M., Dehghan, A., Mudway, I. & Sonia Dagnino, S. 2020. What is new in the exposome? *Environment International*, Volume 143, October 2020, 105887. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.105887>

Von Lindern, E., Lymeus, F. & Hartig, T. (2017). The restorative environment: A complementary concept for salutogenesis studies. In: Mittelmark, M. B., Sagy, S., Eriksson, M., Bauer, G. F., Pellikan, J., Lindström, B. & Espnes, G. A. (Eds.). *The Handbook of Salutogenesis* (Chapter 19). Springer DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-04600-6

Vriend J L, Davidson F D, Corkum P V, Rusak B, McLaughlin E N. Chambers C T (2012) Sleep Quantity and Quality in Relation to Daytime Functioning in Children, *Children's Health Care*, 41:3, 204-222.

Walker, D. I., Valvi, D., Rothman, N., Lan, Q., Miller, G. W. & Jones, D. P. 2019. The Metabolome: a Key Measure for Exposome Research in Epidemiology. *Current Epidemiology Reports*, 6, 93–103

Weich, S., Brugha, T., King, M., McManus, S., Bebbington, P., Jenkins, R., . . . Stewart-Brown, S. (2011). Mental well-being and mental illness: findings from the Adult Psychiatric Morbidity Survey for England 2007. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 199(1), 23-28

Wild, C. J. 2005. Complementing the Genome with an “Exposome”: The Outstanding Challenge of Environmental Exposure Measurement in Molecular Epidemiology. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev*. 2005 Aug;14(8):1847-50. DOI: 10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-05-0456

Willoughby, M.; Hong, Y.; Hudson, K.; & Wylie, A. (2020). Between- and within-person contributions of simple reaction time to executive function skills in early childhood. *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 192, 104779.

World Health Organization. (1995). The World Health Organization Quality of Life assessment (WHOQOL): position paper from the World Health Organization. *Social Science & Medicine* 41(10), 1403-1409

World Health Organization. 2001. www.inchem.org/documents/ehc/ehc/ehc222.htm

World Health Organization. (2004). Promoting Mental Health; Concepts emerging evidence and practice. Summary report Geneva.

Zelazo, D.Z. (2015). Executive function: Reflection, iterative reprocessing, complexity, and the developing brain. *Developmental Review*, 38, 55-68.4

7. Annex

7.1 Annex 1: Mental health outcomes

Mental health outcomes in the Equal-Life project	
Description of concept	Key measures/aspects for the concept
Mental health (or mental ill-health or illness)	
Psychological or psychiatric illness or psychological ill-health (psychopathology)	Psychiatric diagnoses - ICD-10/DSM-V or equivalent <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADHD • Depression • Anxiety Symptom measures Internalizing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional symptoms (SDQ)⁴ Externalizing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct problems (SDQ) • Inattention/Hyperactivity (SDQ) Thought Disorder <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-relationship problems (SDQ)
Well-being, or positive mental health	
“a state of well-being in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to her or his community”	Hedonic well-being <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Happiness • Life satisfaction • Interest in life Eudaemonic well-being <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal growth • Relationships • Optimal functioning Feeling well <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pleasure • Happiness • Emotional satisfaction Doing well <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptational success, i.e., mastering of developmental tasks faced by children of a given age in a specific socio-cultural context Psychological well-being Social well-being Emotional-well-being Standardised or established measures of well-being

⁴ The Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire is available in many Equal Life cohorts. Other similar scale measures of psychological symptoms may be available in some cohorts.

D 5.5 - Final Requirements for Multimodal Exposome

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warwick Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale • KINDL <p>Quality of life</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life satisfaction • Functioning • Health-related quality of life • Life satisfaction • Emotional well-being
The general factor of psychopathology (the p-factor)	Total Difficulties Score (SDQ; adding the scores for hyperactivity, emotional symptoms, conduct problems and peer problems)
Mediating moderating factors (To be further developed)	
Other biological, physical and social exposures relevant for mental health and well-being	<p>Resilience</p> <p>Sense of coherence</p> <p>Self-esteem</p> <p>Self-efficacy</p> <p>Personality (neuroticism)</p> <p>Temperament</p> <p>Maturation</p> <p>Development</p> <p>Coping skills</p> <p>Sleep</p> <p>Self-regulation</p> <p>Stress</p> <p>Restoration</p> <p>Attachment</p>

7.2 Annex 2: Cognitive outcomes

Domain-general cognitive functions					
Executive Functions					
Processing Speed	Basic Executive Functions			Higher-level Executive Functions	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple reaction time • Crossing-out-tasks • Visual matching tasks 	<u>Working memory:</u> Holding information in mind and working with it <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • digit span backwards • reading span • operation span • running memory • n-back 	<u>Inhibitory Control</u> (of attention and action) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • flanker task • stroop task • go-nogo task • Stop-signal task 	<u>Cognitive Flexibility</u> (Set Shifting /Switching) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dimensional Card Sorting • Number-letter-task • Switch tasks 	<u>Reasoning & Problem-solving</u> Tests of general intelligence, e.g., <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raven SPM/CPM • Culture Fair Test (CFT) • SON-R 	<u>Planning</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tower of Hanoi
Long-term memory: Episodic Memory					
Encoding, Storage, Retrieval of Events e.g., Retelling a story heard 2 hours ago; Recognizing Pictures seen 2 hours before)					

Language functions				
Oral Language Functions				
<u>Phonology</u>	<u>Semantics</u>	<u>Syntax</u>	<u>Listening Comprehension</u>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speech perception in noise • Speech sound discrimination • EEG Parameters of speech processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vocabulary (receptive/productive) • Conceptual Knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sentence production • Sentence comprehension • sentence repetition 	Retelling a story ; answering questions	
Written Language Functions				
Precursors of Literacy Functions			Literacy Functions: Reading, Spelling, Writing	
<u>Verbal short-term memory,</u> e.g. digit span, word span, nonword repetition	<u>Phonological Awareness</u> e.g., blending, segmentation, manipulation of speech sounds in words	<u>Rapid Naming</u> (words presented pictorially)	<u>Decoding</u> (reading and spelling words)	<u>Reading comprehension and fluency</u>

7.3 Annex 3: Stress-related mechanisms

Stress-related mediators in the Equal-Life project	
Description of concept	Key measures/aspects for the concept
Stress	<p>Stress occurs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • within a process in which an environmental demand tax or exceeds <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the natural regulatory capacity of an organism or ○ the adaptive capacity or ○ available coping resources of an individual or ○ perceived discrepancy between what is expected to be 'normal' and what is happening in reality • when people experience threatening or loss of resources, or an investment of sources without subsequent gain. <p>Stress occurs on an acute level and in association with other concepts such as perceived loss of control/learned helplessness, lack of coping capacity, lack of restoration or no/restricted access to restorative environment can lead to chronic stress (psychological distress), mental disorders and impairment of cognitive functions.</p>
Psychological stress	<p>Stress</p> <p>Person-Environment-Fit</p> <p>Appraisal (of stress situations): primary, secondary, reappraisal</p>
Stressors:	life events, trauma, daily hassles, ambient stressor, environmental stressor, family stress, prenatal stress
Responses:	worries, fear, startle, anxiety, (feeling of) discomfort, exhaustion, rumination, tension
	response related to environmental stressor (external exposome): annoyance, disturbance, (perceived) impairment
Situational factors	(un-)controllability, (un-)predictability, (lack of) restoration, (lack of) access to restorative environment
Coping	coping (strategies), resistance, adaptation
Personal (moderating) factors	vulnerability, resilience, (loss of) optimism, pessimism, perceived control, (learned) helplessness
Examples of measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LECI: Life Events and Coping Inventory; age: 12-14 years; Dese-Lewis (1988) - experience of life stress - the use of coping behaviours - PSS: Perceived stress scale; age: 14 years + (at least junior high school education); Cohen et al. (1983) - widely used instrument for measuring the degree to which situations are perceived as stressful - conceptualized as one-factor scale; research suggest and confirms two-factor structure: perceived helplessness (response to stress), perceived self-efficacy (self-assessed coping ability) - SSKJ 3-8 R: Fragebogen zur Erhebung von Stress und Stressbewältigung im Kindes- und Jugendalter - Revision (<i>questionnaire for the assessment of stress and coping in childhood</i>)

Stress-related mediators in the Equal-Life project	
Description of concept	Key measures/aspects for the concept
	<p><i>and adolescence – revised</i>); age: 3rd- 8th grade; Lohaus et al. (2018)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vulnerability for potential stressors - Coping potential (strategies) - Physiological and psychological symptoms related to stress - Well-being scale
(Psycho-) physiological stress indices, key terms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Saliva (e.g. cortisol) - Urine (e.g. catecholamines, cortisol) - cortisol (e.g. in hair) - hypothalamic pituitary adrenal axis or HPA axis - ACTH - Glucocorticoid - Norepinephrine, epinephrine - Noradrenaline, or adrenaline - sympathetic nervous system - Heart blood pressure - Heart rate - Heart rate variability (HRV) - allostatic load - homeostase

7.4 Annex 4: Restoration-related mechanisms

Restoration-related mediators in the Equal-Life project	
Description of concept	Key measures/aspects for the concept
Restoration – Process through which adaptive capacities diminished in ongoing efforts to meet adaptive demands are renewed, recovered, or re-established	
Actual restoration – Recovery of cognitive or other resources following exposure to a taxing environmental stimulus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective measures of change in emotion, physiology, cognition, and behaviour (e.g. cognitive tests, sympathetic/parasympathetic nervous system activation, blood pressure, salivary cortisol, and positive/negative affect) <u>in relation to a setting or activity</u> <p>Not available in cohorts. Can be employed in planned field studies.</p>
Perceived restoration – Perceptions of the effect of restorative experience or how one restored one feels in some spatial or activity context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-reported measures of change in emotion, physiology, cognition, and behaviour (e.g., ability to stay focused and alert, clear one’s thoughts from worries, remember things, feeling relaxed, and non-specific physiological symptoms), <u>in relation to a setting or activity</u> <p>Available scales in the cohorts used to measure, e.g., mental health, well-being, cognition, stress may contain single restoration-relevant items. These can be useful to proxy perceived restoration, if they can be linked to a particular environment, surroundings, setting or activity (pre-post difference or perceptions of the effect of repeated exposures/experiences)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific tools for measuring perceived restoration (e.g., ROS, RSS, RS) <p>Not available in cohorts. Can be employed in planned field studies.</p>
Restorativeness/restorative quality – Potential restorative capacity of environment, surroundings, setting or activity	
Perceived restorative quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Items on perceived environmental quality (e.g., aesthetic quality, quietness, opportunities to play, safety) may overlap with restorative quality <p>Available in the cohorts (e.g., Alpine study).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specific tools for measuring perceived restorativeness (e.g., PRS, PRCS, PRS-C, PRSS) <p>Not available in cohorts. Can be employed in planned field studies and by adding enhanced information by WPs 3, 4 and 5</p>
Objective restorative quality – Availability or accessibility to environments where “stressors” are absent or environmental attributes elicit fascination or promote acquisition of new adaptive resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distance to natural outdoor spaces (green/blue), recreational facilities, etc. Amount of natural outdoor spaces around school/home (e.g., NDVI, tree cover, % land use) Presence of amenities like playgrounds, parks, dog zones, gathering places (by design) Indicators of aesthetic beauty, biodiversity, quietness <p>Available in the cohorts after data enrichment by WPs 3, 4 and 5</p>
Instoration – A construct closely related to restoration; that is, an environment of high restorative quality can afford opportunities to acquire new adaptive resources, and in turn both can work together to support mental health/ cognition and foster health in general.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical activity, social interaction, etc. <u>in relation to a setting or activity</u> <p>Available in the cohorts.</p>

7.5 Annex 5: Sleep-related mechanisms

Table 4. Sleep related mediators in the Equal-Life project	
Domains	Key terms
Measures of sleep quantity and sleep pattern	Polysomnogram (PSG), Electroencephalogram (EEG), electro-oculogram (EOG) and muscle-tone (electromyogram (EMG) Heart rate (HR) Rapid Eye Movement (REM), non-REM, N1, N2, N3 (slow wave sleep SWS) awake, waking up after sleep onset (WASO), arousal, sleep latency, sleep duration.
Measures of sleep quality	Sleep quality, time to fall asleep, restorative properties of sleep. Bedtime resistance, Night awakenings, parasomnia* nightmares “night terrors” dysomnia.
Sleep related outcomes (short term)	Insomnia, parasomnia, fatigue, mood, emotional control.
Sleep related behaviour	Performance, tiredness, mood, irritation
Time	Night, nocturnal, circadian rhythm, overnight, evening, morning

7.6 Annex 6: Self-regulation and coping-related mechanisms

Self-regulation and coping related mediators in Equal-Life	
Domains	Key terms
Self-regulation: related terms, determinants, long-term outcomes, measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-regulation, emotion regulation, resilience - emotion understanding, temperament, attachment security, social support, self-esteem, self-efficacy, personal control, perceived control, locus of control, helplessness, controllability, uncontrollability, attributional style, explanatory style, causal attribution, outcome expectancy, optimism, sense of coherence - adaptation, adjustment - delay of gratification, gambling, questionnaires (self-report, parent report, teacher report)
Coping and coping styles	Coping, rumination, avoidance, disengagement, withdrawal, denial, distraction, disengagement, reappraisal, restructuring, problem-solving, acceptance, emotional venting, support seeking, information seeking, social referencing

7.7 Annex 7. Definitions of shortlisted exposures

Short-listed variables of relevance in Equal-Life with their definitions	
Variables	Definition
Outdoor Quality	
Air quality outdoor Residential /school/preschool	The state of the air around us. Good air quality refers to clean, clear, unpolluted air.
Sound/Noise quality outdoor Residential/school/preschool Outdoor	Unwanted or harmful outdoor sound created by human activity, such as noise emitted by means of transport, road traffic, rail traffic, air traffic and industrial activity.
Outdoor restorative quality	"A deed or place or activity that serves to restore to consciousness, vigor, or health Indicator Perceived Restorative Quality sale" (Hartig)
Housing practices	programs and methods that have been successful in producing affordable housing 2) best practices in housing and neighborhood design.
Indoor Quality	
Mother smoking during pregnancy	NO DEFINITION
Child passive smoking	Passive smoking is the inhalation of smoke, called secondhand smoke, or environmental tobacco smoke.
Indoor environmental quality at home/school/preschool (mould/dust/dampness/overall)	Quality of a building's environment in relation to the health and wellbeing of those who occupy space within it.
Crowding Residential, Preschool and school	Psychology: psychological stress or friction which is generated in settings where the concentration of people to the area is a high ratio.
Indoor Air quality, NO ₂ (as proxy for traffic related air pollution), particulate matter	Quality within and around buildings and structures, especially as it relates to the health and comfort of building occupants.
Indoor Sound, quality	NO DEFINITION
Home toxics/Household chemicals	Non-food chemicals that are commonly found and used in and around the average household.
Prenatal: Mother work chemicals/household chemicals	NO DEFINITION
Built environment	
Density (population, building, activities, distribution of functions)	Geography: the number of things—which could be people, animals, plants, or objects—in a certain area Urban planning: a concept to describe the intensity of people, jobs, housing units, total floor area of buildings, level of human activity across a spatial unit of interest (e.g. urban block, neighbourhood, administrative district)
Amenity (sidewalks, bike-paths, parks, libraries, playgrounds, sport facilities, health food /health care); public transport	Urban planning: a set of land uses that contribute to the liveability of the urban environment

Street integration and connectivity	The acoustic environment as perceived by humans, in context.
Access to healthy food	NO DEFINITION
Public transport lines	NO DEFINITION
Walkability	A metric to capture how friendly an area is to walking. Factors influencing walkability include the presence or absence and quality of footpaths, sidewalks or other pedestrian infrastructure, traffic and road conditions, land use patterns (see also: land use mix), building accessibility, and safety, among others. The density of land uses and the distance to different amenities from a reference point (e.g. residential location, workplace, school) are the main proxies that most walkability indices are based on. However, walkability is more than just access to and quality of destinations — it is also about the safety, comfort, and pleasurability of the walk. Also, the different needs, behaviours, and perceptions of people (e.g. children as opposed to adults) can affect walkability, and this is something that Equal-Life could consider to offer a more comprehensive measure of walkability.
Natural Environment	
Access to green space (residential. Preschool, school, “en route”)	NO DEFINITION
Access to blue space (residential. Preschool, school, “en route”)	NO DEFINITION
Playability	
Safety related to playability	NO DEFINITION
Safety green and blue space	NO DEFINITION
Activities green/blue space	NO DEFINITION
Lifestyle	
Sleep (duration, quality, rhythm)	(See section 3.3.2 in the main body)
Smoking	NO DEFINITION
Substance use	Inappropriate consumption of medicines, drugs, or other materials including prescription drugs, over-the-counter drugs, street drugs, alcohol, and tobacco.
Food: healthy food intake, breast feeding	NO DEFINITION
Activity patterns	Type, amount, and organization of activity that occupies the lives of people on a recurring basis
Mobility/mode of commuting	The movement of people (physical as opposed to social)

D 5.5 - Final Requirements for Multimodal Exposome

Leisure time	Free time when one is not working or attending to other duties or activities
Sports	NO DEFINITION
Sunlight exposure	NO DEFINITION
Playtime Online, Playing Videogames (social media use), Blue light TV watching	Amount of time spent using a device with a screen such as a smartphone, computer, television, or video game console.
Social environment	
Work and income situation, educational background, individual, household, neighborhood level.	Concept to capture the socioeconomic situation of an individual, including factors that can influence household stress (e.g. job insecurity) as well as material means (e.g. income).
Social interaction	Social interactions with different people e.g. peers, teachers, parents, other family members. Includes negative social interactions e.g. experiences of bullying from peers.
Social integration/cohesion/network (e.g. neighbourhood, preschool, school)	Social relationships a person has in different contexts.
Stressful life events	Aspects of family life (e.g. socio-economic situation, parent's depression, abuse, violence), kindergarten and school environment (e.g. discrimination by teacher, being bullied by other, moving to another school, poor grades or poor performances at sports, too much homework), and health issues (e.g. obesity, asthma, allergies, diabetes) as potential psychosocial stressors.
Parenting style and quality and practices	Authoritative and authoritarian parenting, verbal hostility, parental warmth, positive expressivity, friendliness, encouragement, closeness, positive affect, negativity, interactiveness, limit setting, effective responsiveness, respect for autonomy, parental neuroticism and agreeableness.
Parental depression/anxiety	Maternal depression both prenatal and postnatal. Definition varies according to different studies in relation to assessment tools and period definition. Prenatal maternal depression, based on self-reported symptoms during pregnancy (different questionnaires have been used)
Chaotic living conditions	<p>Chaotic living conditions include residential noise and crowding, instability in household occupants/location, and lack of routine and structure in daily life.</p> <p>Residential crowding (more than two people per bedroom) background noise (more than 4 hr per day of television on while child is home), instability (change since child's birth in caregiver's residential partner). Presence of a condition receives a score of 1, with scores combined to create an index.</p>

D 5.5 - Final Requirements for Multimodal Exposome

Family instability	Family instability measured as change since child's birth in caregiver's residential partner (part of the chaotic living conditions)
Support from parents	Maternal responsiveness (e.g., "help with homework", "willing to talk when needed")
Violence/maltreatment	Exposure to violence and victimization by witnessing violence, personal victimization, and witnessing weapon-related violence. Community violence by direct victimization. Parents' report of intimate partner violence.
Caring and household responsibilities	Caregivers working time, household chaos (see above)
Academic stress (child)	Subjective stress that involves frustration associated with academic failure, the feeling of such failure, or even an awareness of the possibility of such failure. Academic stress is a stressed state experienced by students, owing to student stature or academic demands.
Home learning environment	index comprising six mother-reported variables: frequency of child being read to, going to the library, painting and drawing, being taught letters, being taught numbers, and learning songs/poems/rhymes
Resilience/susceptibility (physical/social)	Biological susceptibility and socially determined vulnerability as well as recovery capacity, i.e. resilience.
Quality of school/teaching	NO DEFINITION
Experiences of discrimination (e.g. as a result of sex/gender, sexuality, ethnicity, religious affiliation).	Discrimination experienced as a result of supposed 'deviation' from predominant and accepted social norm.
Social modelling	Social learning through observation and imitation of others e.g. parents, peers.
sex/gender, age, religion, household structure, migration background	NO DEFINITION
Age of the parents	Maternal age during pregnancy, parental age at the moment of data collection
Average rating >= 4	
Average rating between 3 and 4	

7.8 Annex 8: External exposures rejected from the shortlist

External exposures rejected from the shortlist	
Indoor quality	View, Window orientation toward green space
Indoor quality	Light in home, school, preschool
Built Environment *	Mixed Perception of built environment
Built Environment *	Type of Housing
Built Environment *	Soundscape and Landscape appearance
Built Environment *	Access to (mental) healthcare
Built Environment	Mixed Land surface temperature
Built Environment	Land use mix
Built Environment	Impervious area's
Built Environment	Buffer of visibility
Natural Environment	Availability of walking and cycle paths
Natural Environment	Usage Green and Blue space
Natural Environment	Quality of green space (residential, preschool, school), Maintenance, Attractiveness/ usability
Natural Environment	Temperature
Natural Environment	Traffic
Life style	Health behaviour other
Life style	Exposure to Electromagnetic fields
Social Environment *	Political determinants
Social Environment *	Identity (personal identity, social identity)
Social Environment *	Social norms and cultural values

7.9 Annex 9: Overarching research questions identified in Equal-Life

Outline of research questions identified in Equal-Life		
Research question 1-11 Which exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings are associated with [outcome] ?	Research question 12-21 and 22-24 How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with [outcome] ?	
Outcome 1. General cognition 2. Language abilities 3. School achievement 4. Well-being 5. Internalizing symptoms 6. Depression/anxiety 7. Autism 8. Externalizing symptoms 9. ADHD 10. Total difficulties 11. Biomarkers	<u>Mental health and cognitive development outcomes</u> a. How does the irregularity, unpredictability, and duration of social and physical risk factors affect [outcome] in children across their life-course? b. Is there a cumulative effect of the physical indoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on [outcome] later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping? c. Is there a cumulative effect of the physical outdoor environment and social exposome in early life stage on [outcome] later on in life? To what extent is this association mediated by stress/sleep/coping? d. Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do social exposures moderate the effect of physical exposures on the child's [outcome] ? e. Across different life stages of the child, to what extent do physical exposures moderate the effect of social exposures on the child's [outcome] ? f. Does growing up in a supportive social environment modify the negative effects of physical environment on the child's [outcome] ?	Outcome 12. General cognition 13. Language abilities 14. School achievement 15. Well-being 16. Internalizing symptoms 17. Depression/ anxiety 18. Autism 19. Externalizing symptoms 20. ADHD 21. Total difficulties
	<u>Biomarkers</u> 22: How are exposures in residential, pre-school and school settings associated with biomarkers of mental health (identified by WP2)? 22 a. How do internal biomarkers mediate the pathway from physical and social exposures in early life to mental health and cognitive outcomes?	22. Biomarkers (of mental health)
	<u>Child perspective</u> 23: How does a child perspective of exposures differ from an adult's perspective of exposures in relation to the outcomes of interest? 24: How are exposures from a child's perspective associated with outcomes of interest?	23. child perspective exposure 24. child perspective outcome